

.....

DESIGNING INCLUSIVE MUSEUM EXHIBITIONS: A COST-EFFECTIVE APPROACH TO SENSORY ACCESSIBILITY

.....

Irena Ružin, Jove Pargovski
N.I. Institute and Museum Bitola

ABSTRACT

Access to cultural institutions is essential for all individuals. People with disabilities, however, often face significant barriers. This paper details the efforts to enhance museum accessibility for individuals with sensory disabilities in the NI Institute and Museum Bitola. Initially, we discuss the creation of tactile exhibitions, highlighting the challenges encountered and the solutions implemented. Furthermore, we explore the measures taken to improve accessibility for people with hearing and speech impairments. By leveraging QR codes and NFC tags, all visitors can use their own mobile phones as personal guides, thereby enhancing museum accessibility for everyone. The participation of the Balkan Museum Network in the SHIFT project represents the next phase. Through the use of AI and modern technologies, this initiative aims to significantly improve museum accessibility, setting a new standard for inclusivity.

Keywords: museum accessibility, visual impairments, tactile exhibition, SHIFT

INTRODUCTION

People with disabilities often face significant barriers when attempting to visit cultural institutions. Several factors contribute to this limitation, with the most prominent being a lack of information and understanding regarding international and national regulations. Institutions frequently struggle to comprehend their responsibilities related to human rights and other relevant considerations.

Many Balkan museums started to develop projects for accessibility and inclusion in cooperation with the BMAG¹¹. Training sessions and international seminars were organized for the museum staff with the goal of enhancing accessibility and inclusion. These sessions highlighted best practices and emphasized both

11. Since 2010, the Balkan Museum Network has been providing support to Balkan museums through small grants for implementing projects for accessibility. Many museums benefited from these grants, developing tactile exhibitions and access surveys conducted by representatives of the BMAG <https://www.bmmuseums.net/balkan-museum-access-group/>

international and national regulations. The NI Institute and Museum Bitola efforts started with improving physical accessibility with movable ramps and a lift car. This was proposed by the Association of Persons with Physical Disabilities of Bitola, as one of the measures to improve the physical accessibility of an object that is registered as a monument of culture, where there is a limited possibility for architectural interventions.

The same approach was applied to improve accessibility for people with sensory disabilities. Through communication and cooperation with the relevant associations from our country, work began on proposing new solutions to improve accessibility guided by the principle "Nothing About Us Without Us".

TACTILE EXHIBITIONS FOR BLIND AND VISUALLY IMPAIRED VISITORS

The sense of touch holds profound significance for persons who are blind or visually impaired, serving as a gateway to understanding and experiencing the world around them (Levent and McRaine, 2014). Recognizing the pivotal role of touch in the lives of persons who are blind, museums have increasingly embraced the creation of tactile exhibits. By offering multisensory encounters through tactile displays, museums strive to democratize access to art, history, and culture, ensuring that everyone can engage with and appreciate their collections regardless of visual ability. These tactile exhibits not only empower visitors who are blind to independently explore and interpret artefacts but also foster empathy and understanding among sighted visitors, thereby promoting a more inclusive and diverse museum experience.

Two elements are essential for a successful tactile representation: a tactile object and its description.

The tactile object in some cases can be the museum object itself. It would be ideal if all museum objects were available to be touched. However, as touching is prohibited in most cases, an appropriate solution could be to use a representative tactile copy.

A "true copy" made of same material would be ideal, but sometimes these are expensive or impossible to produce. Also, many times the object itself in its original form cannot convey any message to the persons who are blind (for example - the elements cannot be distinguished from each other when touched), so it is necessary to create a tactile representation with more pronounced elements (Picture 1.c). Thus, tactile objects can be created using paper, plaster, 3D printing or some other technique or material (Candlin, 2008).

The second important element is the description of the object, crucial for making tactile objects accessible and meaningful for persons who are blind or visually impaired. Tactile objects rely on touch, so detailed descriptions provide the essential context, guide exploration, and aid comprehension. Descriptions bridge

a. 3D printed tactile map of the Heraclea Lyncestis archaeological site near Bitola

b. Plaster copy of the Tragic Mask of Heraclea Lyncestis (reduced size)

c. Enlarged plaster copy of a coin portraying Alexander the Great

the physical object and the individual's understanding, offering details like shape, texture, size, and spatial relationships to create a mental image. Descriptions also provide interpretive information not obvious through touch alone, such as the object's historical or cultural context, function, significance, and symbolic elements. This enriches the understanding and appreciation of the object (Asakawa, et al. 2018).

Descriptions can be divided into two types:

- **Object Description:** Explains the object's uniqueness, importance, and exhibition context using clear and concise language to create an engaging story for all visitors.
- **Navigational Description:** Specifically for persons who are blind, this type of description provides instructions on what the tactile object represents, whether a 2D drawing or 3D copy.

The first tactile exhibition in the NI Institute and museum Bitola was organized in 2018 with the support of the Balkan Museum Network. This initiative aimed to improve accessibility for persons who are blind or visually impaired individuals. Tactile images, inspired by objects from the permanent exhibition, were displayed on panels with Braille descriptions and accompanying pictures for sighted individuals. An audio narration accessible via QR code was also provided.

The exhibition was enthusiastically received by blind individuals nationwide and soon followed requests for the exhibition to visit other cities. Many museums adopted this approach, including institutions in Macedonia, Montenegro, and Serbia. Additionally, exhibitions were held in museums in Slovenia, Croatia, Bosnia and Herzegovina and Serbia. The objects on the tactile images were selected from the permanent collection of the museum in Bitola, promoting the rich cultural heritage of the Bitola region.

Figure 2. Portable tactile exhibition with motifs from the museum objects from the NI institute and Museum Bitola, presented on tactile panels

ENHANCING MUSEUM ACCESSIBILITY WITH SIGN LANGUAGE VIDEOS AND QR CODES

Figure 3. QR code next to the museum object

Initially, QR codes were unfamiliar to many visitors at our first tactile exhibition in 2018, so we provided informational flyers with aid usage instructions. The first part of the tactile object - the description, the object's story, is universally translatable and can also be presented through audio narrations or sign language videos, also enhancing engagement and accessibility for persons who are deaf or hard of hearing.

Figure 4. Museum in a suitcase- tactile copies

By scanning the QR code, visitors can access the museum website for more information, including sign language videos, high-quality photos with zooming capabilities, and even 3D reconstructions for some objects.

This initiative marked the first self-guided tour tailored for the people who are deaf and hard of hearing, offering them a deeper understanding of Bitola's heritage. Simultaneously, object descriptions elevated the experience for sighted visitors, resulting in an improved museum experience for all museum visitors.

Picture 3 shows a QR code placed next to the museum object in the permanent museum exhibit.

Figure 5. 3 D model of the Museum building

By scanning the code, visitors open the appropriate section on the website, where more information is provided: narration, a sign language video and a high quality photo with the possibility of zooming in. By using this approach, we have managed to bring the museum collection closer to a much larger number of visitors in a relatively cost-effective and simple way. The objects are accessible to all visitors around the world 24/7. Through the use of sign language videos, the museum exhibit has been made more accessible to people who are hearing and speech impaired, while audio narrations allow visitors' smartphones to serve as their personal museum guides, without the need to install software.

Each new visit to the exhibition and each new object led to an improvement in access and an increase in the collection with new "tactile" objects. The "Museum in a Suitcase" was a project created in cooperation with the Homeland Museum of Knjaževac, Serbia (Picture 4) that included copies made of material similar or identical to the original object.

For immovable cultural heritage objects, such as the museum building, 3D printing was utilized (Picture 5). This created smaller-scale replicas to help people who are blind or visually impaired understand their shape. Additionally, these 3D prints could be used to craft tactile maps showcasing the city center's key features.

NFC TAGS AND THE AIM OF ACHIEVING FULL INDEPENDENCE FOR BLIND AND VISUALLY IMPAIRED VISITORS

During the initial exhibitions, it became evident that, in order to visit museums, people with visual impairments still dependent on the assistance they get from their family, friends or from the museum personnel. This dependence stems from challenges such as navigating spaces not being designed for people who are blind, or the inability to read Braille. Braille illiteracy is a significant obstacle, limiting the persons who are blind or visually impaired from accessing crucial information and hindering their educational and professional prospects.

In Europe, approximately 5% of people who are blind can read Braille. Globally, the highest percentage is in the USA, at around 10% (Asakawa, S. et al. 2018).

Starting from our belief that modern technologies should complement Braille, we have started to integrate modern technologies to enhance the accessibility. Initially, we provided audio narration alongside Braille text, accessible online via smartphones. As many people who are blind are smartphone users, this approach proved effective. For those without smartphones, museum staff offered devices during the exhibition. To streamline the access, assistants scanned QR codes to open relevant audio narrations for tactile objects. Later, we explored the use of NFC tags.

Figure 6. Proposed design of a tactile exhibition space, in which NFC tags are used

In the realm of tactile museum experiences, NFC (Near Field Communication) tags emerge as a ground-breaking tool (Blöckner et al., 2009). These tiny, unobtrusive tags discreetly embedded within museum exhibits hold the power to transform static objects into gateways of rich auditory description.

Near Field Communication (NFC) is a short-range wireless technology that allows devices to communicate when they are close to each other, typically within a few centimeters (Blöckner et al., 2009).

Imagine a scenario like the one shown in Picture 6: A blind or visually impaired visitor enters the exhibition space and taps their smartphone on a designated NFC tag (1). This action provides them with navigational and other relevant information about the exhibition. By tapping their smartphone on additional NFC tags placed at tactile images (2) or 3D replicas (3), visitors instantly receive tailored audio descriptions. This level of autonomy empowers visually impaired individuals to explore museum collections independently and at their own pace, enhancing their understanding and connection to the exhibits.

The versatility of NFC technology allows for flexibility and scalability in creating accessible museum experiences. Curators can easily update or customize audio descriptions to cater to diverse audiences or accommodate temporary exhibitions, ensuring that inclusivity should remain at the forefront of museum accessibility initiatives.

Ultimately, NFC tags revolutionize tactile museum experiences, foster inclusivity, innovation, and engagement for all visitors, regardless of their visual ability.

THE SHIFT PROJECT

The approach explained earlier and the activities described have proven to be successful tools for improving the accessibility of museum exhibits. However, modern trends and technologies offer many new possibilities, that will significantly improve the accessibility of museums.

Since 2023, the Balkan Museum Network has been a member of the SHIFT project (Metamorphosis of cultural Heritage Into augmented hypermedia assets For enhanced accessibility and inclusion supports the adoption of digital transformation strategies and the uptake of tools within the creative and cultural industries - CCI).

SHIFT is a part of a cluster of six projects funded under HORIZON Europe and it leverages advances in Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) to improve cultural heritage access for European citizens experiencing sensory impairment. It aims to enrich the experience of interacting with cultural assets through visual, auditory, and sensory modalities, e.g., using haptics.

SHIFT also develops tools and methodologies to enable contemporary description of cultural assets through language evolution models. Results are thematically clustered into visual-auditory-haptics components:

- Visual toolkit: using AI and ML algorithms will enable automatic transcription of the cultural heritage content. The toolkit will identify objects and actions, which assist in transcribing the historical depictions at economies of scale.
- Auditory toolkit: the toolkit will deliver an emotional response to the audience by using advances in auditory synthesizers. Human-like correspondence will minimise barriers for effective interaction by people with sensory impairments.
- Haptics toolkit: this will enable multi-sensory interaction with digital objects, through a novel approach which delivers haptic feedback emulating the feeling of touch in a digital object.
- IPR toolkit: To address the challenge of protecting the digital native content, SHIFT will adopt international standards on copyrights and digital protection of derivative copyrights.

CONCLUSION

The integration of new technologies such as smartphones, QR codes, NFC, and AI into the permanent and tactile exhibits at the NI Institute and Museum Bitola holds tremendous potential for enhancing accessibility for people with sensory disabilities. These innovations enable personalized and adaptable experiences, that cater to the specific needs of visitors. The use of QR codes and NFC tags within the exhibit, combined with visitors' personal smartphones, transforms these devices into personal guides, providing audio descriptions and sign language videos that make the exhibits more inclusive and engaging. AI technologies further enhance accessibility by offering sophisticated tools, such as those mentioned in the SHIFT project. Together, these advancements contribute to creating a more inclusive museum environment. The latest developments in AI technologies open up a wide range of possibilities, which, combined with our experience in improving accessibility, are steadily leading us toward the goal of an inclusive museum environment where all visitors can fully enjoy and benefit from our exhibits.

REFERENCES

Asakawa, S., Guerreiro, J., Ahmetovic, D., Kitani, K. M., & Asakawa, C. (2018). The present and future of museum accessibility for people with visual impairments. In Proceedings of the 20th International ACM SIGACCESS Conference on Computers and Accessibility (ASSETS '18) <https://doi.org/10.1145/3234695.3240999>

Blöckner, A. M., Danti, S., Forrai, J., Broll, G., & De Luca, A. (2009). Please touch the exhibits! using NFC-based interaction for exploring a museum. In Proceedings of the 11th Conference on Human-Computer Interaction with Mobile Devices and Services (Mobile-HCI '09)

Candlin, F. (2008). Touch, and the limits of the rational museum or can matter think? . Available at https://www.researchgate.net/publication/36725962_Touch_and_the_Limits_of_the_Rational_Museum_or_Can_Matter_Think

International Organization for Standardization ISO/IEC 18092:2023 Information technology -- Telecommunications and information exchange between systems – Near Field Communication Interface and Protocol 1 (NFCIP-1). Retrieved from <https://www.iso.org/standard/82095.html>

Levent, N., & McRaney, D. L. (2014). Touch and narrative in art and history museums. In N. Levent & A. Pascual-Leone (Eds.), *The multisensory museum: Cross-disciplinary perspectives on touch, sound, smell, memory, and space* (pp. [61-85e]). Rowman & Littlefield. Available at https://www.academia.edu/11406938/The_Multisensory_Museum

National Federation of the Blind Jernigan Institute. (2009, March 26). *The Braille Literacy Crisis in America: Facing the Truth, Reversing the Trend, Empowering the Blind* [Report]. Available at https://nfb.org/images/nfb/documents/pdf/braille_literacy_report_web.pdf